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**PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SINGLE CARRIER NON-
ORTHOGONAL MULTIPLE ACCESS (SC-NOMA) IN MULTI-USER
COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS: CAPACITY LIMITATIONS AND
TRADE-OFFS**

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Abstract

This research presents a comprehensive result analysis of a Single Carrier Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access system under various scenarios involving increasing transmitted power and the number of multiplexed users. The primary goal is to achieve valuable insights into the capacity limitations and trade-offs associated with SC-NOMA as the amount of users grows. The simulated data showcases the system's performance and highlights the advantages of SC-NOMA instead of traditional OMA plans. The data analysis reveals that as the quantity of users in the SC-NOMA system increase, there is an increase in the network's entire capacity, demonstrating the effectiveness of power allocation and superposition coding. Users having weaker channel conditions receive higher power allocation, leading to improved data rates compared to OMA schemes. The system exhibits higher spectral efficiency, fairness, and overall capacity in multi-user scenarios.

Keywords: Performance Analysis, Power Optimization, Fairness, Path Loss, Capacity, Fairness.

1. INTRODUCTION

We now connect, communicate, and engage with the world around us in entirely new ways thanks to the development of wireless communication as a breakthrough technology. Each generation has provided ground-breaking innovations that have impacted the contemporary era of connection, from its humble beginnings with first-generation (1G) voice networks to the high-speed, data-driven networks of 5G. There is tremendous expectation for the game-changing capabilities that the sixth generation (6G), the upcoming wireless communication milestone, is planned to bring as we set out on our path towards it.

Faster, more dependable, and ubiquitous connectivity have been the driving forces behind the development and expansion of wireless communication Chen et al (2021). The amount of data has grown dramatically as a result of the extensive use of smartphones, IoT devices, and upcoming technologies like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR). To meet the growing need for data capacity, low latency, and seamless connectivity, researchers and industry participants are assiduously developing 6G networks.

The International Telecommunication Union Radiocommunication Sector's (ITU) 6G vision calls

July : Theme 2

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for a revolutionary user experience and the provision of new kinds of sensory data and experiences Liu et al (2020). This challenging objective will be accomplished by combining cutting-edge concepts, architectures, protocols, and solutions that will go beyond current network paradigms and technology Jin et al (2021). First-generation (1G) networks were introduced in the 1980s, marking the beginning of wireless communication. Although they had some limitations, these analogue voice networks served as the cornerstone for mobile communication. A major turning point was the switch to second-generation (2G) networks, which provided digital communication and allowed for text messaging and data transmission. A more connected world was made possible by the expansion of mobile communication through 2G networks. Third-generation (3G) networks brought higher data transfer rates, internet access, and multimedia services to wireless communication, ushering in a new era of worldwide coverage.

The widespread use of smartphones and the mobile internet revolution were both made possible by 3G networks. Fourth-generation (4G) networks were created in response to the desire for even faster data rates and better user experiences. The advent of 4G networks marked the beginning of the mobile broadband era by offering notable advancements in data speeds, low latency, and network efficiency. Numerous applications, like as video streaming, online gaming, and IoT deployments, were made possible by this approach Chen et al (2020). Researchers and industry professionals started imagining the future of wireless communication as 4G networks became commonplace, including the revolutionary possibilities of 5G and the prospects of 6G.

The intelligence of network components, architecture, and linked devices are all included in intelligent connection, which improves the communication system's overall effectiveness and performance. In order to provide seamless interactions between devices and their surroundings, deep connection places an emphasis on the integration of sensing, learning, and cognitive capabilities. Holographic connectivity enables seamless and high-fidelity coverage for AR, VR, and XR experiences by enabling ubiquitous communication anywhere, at any time. A totally integrated and connected information ecosystem is ensured by ubiquitous connectivity, which strives to provide all-terrain and all-space multiple-dimensional coverage links Sihlbom et al (2022).

Recently, Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access has been receiving a lot of interest, is one of the most promising technologies. NOMA offers increased spectrum efficiency and user fairness, representing a paradigm shift in multiple access methods. NOMA is positioned to play a crucial aspect in the creation of 6G networks, considerably enhancing capabilities of wireless communication, thanks to its potential to support a huge number of connections and a variety of applications Ni et al (2021). NOMA is one of the essential tools for fulfilling the challenging objectives of 6G networks. The cutting-edge multiple access method known as NOMA enables the same time-frequency resources shared by numerous users.

Contrary to conventional OMA systems, NOMA divides users according to their power outputs and decoding priorities. NOMA increases spectrum efficiency and may support more users while utilizing the same resources by the use of superposition coding and successive interference cancellation (SIC). NOMA is a key technology in the implementation of 6G networks because of

the higher capacity, improved user fairness, and decreased latency that arise from this improved efficiency Cui et al (2018).

2. RELATED WORK

NOMA, which aims to increase spectrum utilization and handle an enormous amount of links, has emerged as a viable multi-access approach for future communications networks. Ding et al (2017) investigated the application of MIMO in Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access systems, highlighting the benefits of the transmitting device and receiver employing numerous antennas. Saito and Benjebbour (2013) analyzed the downstream NOMA's at the system level efficiency., revealing its potential advantages over traditional OMA schemes in multi-cell environments. Dai et al. (2015) given a thorough explanation of NOMA for 5G, analyzing issues, difficulties, and potential directions for further study. In large-scale cooperative relay networks, Liu et al. (2017) explored NOMA's application and analyzed system performance under various relay selection and power allocation schemes. Xu et al. (2015) evaluated the performance of NOMA with random beamforming, demonstrating its system capacity and outage probability under different scenarios.

Hassan et al. (2016) conducted a survey on power-domain Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in 5G systems, discussing potentials, difficulties, enabling technologies, and resource allocation methods. NOMA has also been studied in the context of multiple access in cognitive radio networks by Shin and Shin (2018). They proposed a dynamic user clustering scheme for NOMA in cognitive radio networks, demonstrating improved spectrum efficiency. Yang et al. (2019) investigated the impact of inter-cell interference in NOMA-based heterogeneous networks and proposed a resource allocation algorithm to mitigate interference and optimize system performance. In vehicular communication systems, NOMA has been explored as viable way to improve connectivity.

Wang et al. (2018) proposed a NOMA-based cooperative communication scheme for vehicular networks, ensuring reliable and efficient communication among vehicles. Liu et al. (2017) addressed the issues with user connection and resource allocation in NOMA enabled vehicle-to-vehicle communication systems to achieve better performance. Energy-efficient Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access schemes have also been looked into in wireless-powered communication systems. Zhang et al. (2018) developed a resource allocation plan that is energy-efficient in NOMA-based wireless-powered communication systems to maximize the sum energy efficiency.

Ding et al. (2016) studied a resource distribution that is efficient in terms of energy in NOMA-based wireless-powered communication networks. Furthermore, machine learning techniques have been employed to optimize NOMA systems. Zhao et al. (2018) suggested a solution for allocating energy based on deep learning of Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in massive MIMO systems, achieving significant performance gains.

Jiang et al. (2018) used reinforcement learning to optimize power allocation in NOMA-based cooperative networks, achieving enhanced system performance. NOMA has been explored in the context of underwater acoustic communication as well. Yang et al. (2018) suggested a NOMA-based cooperative communication scheme for underwater acoustic sensor networks, ensuring

July : Theme 2

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reliable and efficient data transmission. In addition to the physical layer, NOMA has been applied to improve security in wireless communication systems. Ghasemi et al. (2016) proposed a secure NOMA scheme, enhancing secrecy performance in multiuser networks by exploiting the superposition property of NOMA. Overall, NOMA has garnered the scientific establishment's focus as a result of its potential benefits in enhancing spectral efficiency, supporting massive connectivity, and optimizing resource allocation in various wireless communication scenarios. Several research works have focused on investigating the result of distance on the effectiveness of NOMA-based networks. Ding et al. (2017) conducted a comprehensive survey on MIMO-NOMA systems, highlighting the potential advantages and challenges of employing NOMA in future wireless systems. Saito and Benjebbour (2013) discussed the application of NOMA in cellular radio access, emphasizing its potential for future wireless communication.

Dai et al. (2015) presented solutions, challenges, and opportunities for employing NOMA in 5G networks and discussed future research trends in this area. Liu et al. (2017) studied cooperative NOMA in large-scale relay networks, exploring its advantages in enhancing network capacity and reliability. Studies have also explored the result of distance on the effectiveness of NOMA-based networks in various scenarios. Xu et al. (2015) analyzed the performance of NOMA in large-scale networks with random beamforming and investigated the effects of distance on the system's efficiency.

Wang et al. (2018) proposed a NOMA-based cooperative communication scheme for vehicle-to-vehicle networks, taking into account the result of distance on the overall system performance. Liu et al. (2017) considered user pairing and resource allocation for NOMA-enabled vehicle-to-vehicle communication systems, studying the impact of distance on user grouping and performance optimization. Furthermore, the distance between users and base stations plays an important role in determining the effectiveness of NOMA systems. Zhang et al. (2018) focused on effective distribution of power for NOMA-based wireless-powered communication systems and assessed how distance affected the energy consumption and system throughput. Ding et al. (2016) explored the application of Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access in LTE and 5G networks, highlighting how distance affects system performance and capacity.

Zhao et al. (2018) investigated power allocation in massive MIMO systems using deep learning-based techniques, considering the distance as an essential factor in optimizing the system performance. The distance-dependent nature of NOMA systems is also evident in cooperative networks. Jiang et al. (2018) proposed a method for allocating power based on reinforced learning in cooperative NOMA networks, where the impact of distance on user cooperation and power allocation strategies was analyzed.

Yang et al. (2018) introduced a cooperative communication scheme for underwater acoustic sensor networks based on NOMA, taking into account the impact of distance on signal propagation and system performance. Moreover, the security aspects of NOMA systems are also affected by distance. Ghasemi et al. (2016) addressed the issue of secure communication in multiuser NOMA networks, investigating the impact of distance on the system's vulnerability to eavesdropping and

unauthorized access.

3. METHODOLOGY

NOMA breaks the capacity restrictions of conventional orthogonal multiple access techniques by allowing a number of individuals can communicate simultaneously over the same frequency carrier. NOMA uses a method known as successive interference cancellation (SIC) to successfully handle this difficulty despite the existence of interference brought on by concurrent transmissions. Receivers can intelligently decode and remove interference with the help of SIC, ensuring trustworthy data recovery. Monte Carlo simulations are computer techniques for simulating and analyzing complicated systems or issues that contain uncertainty and unpredictability. The method bears the name of the renowned Monte Carlo Casino, which is famous for its games of chance and probability. Numerous random sampling procedures are used in these simulations to estimate numerical values and statistical outcomes.

The creation of random numbers is the foundation of Monte Carlo simulations. In order to generate random samples from probability distributions reflecting uncertain variables or parameters in the system being modelled, many procedures are used. Monte Carlo simulations try to approximate numerical findings that would be difficult or impossible to achieve analytically by modelling the system using a large number of random samples.

The simulations tend to converge towards more precise estimates as the number of samples rises. Conclusions from Monte Carlo simulations are frequently based on statistical analysis. In order to determine how the system would behave, they compute the averages, variances, and other statistical features of the collected random samples. Monte Carlo simulations used in wireless communication systems to evaluate the performance of various protocols, coding schemes, power distributions, and channel conditions. Researchers can analyze system behaviour in a variety of circumstances using these simulations, which can help them improve performance and make wise judgements based on statistical data. The strength of Monte Carlo simulations rests in their capacity to offer insightful analyses into the behaviour of complex systems under unknown conditions.

During coding in superposition at the side of transmitter, the arranged users based on their channel conditions, and the power allocation follows a specific order, where the weakest user receives the highest power allocation. Suppose there are K users, and their channels are ordered such that $|h_1|^2 < |h_2|^2 < \dots < |h_K|^2$. Then, the corresponding power allocation coefficients are arranged as $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2 > \dots > \alpha_K$. Specifically, we need to ensure that the allocation of power to the weakest user (α_1) is greater than the sum of powers allocated to all the other users ($\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \dots + \alpha_K$), and similarly, the allocation of power to second weakest user (α_2) is greater than the sum of powers allocated to remaining users ($\alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + \dots + \alpha_K$). This pattern continues for all users, where the power allocated to k^{th} weakest user (α_k) should be greater than the sum of powers

allocated to the users with indices $K+1$ to K .

Fig 1: Block representation of data flow

4. RESULT ANALYSIS

The main purpose of this result analysis is to acquire essential concepts into the capacity limitations and trade-offs associated with SC-NOMA as the number of multiplexed user's increases. By analyzing the simulated data, we aim to understand the system's performance under different scenarios and draw evidence-based conclusions on the efficacy of SC-NOMA in multi-user communication systems. When the user number increases in the SC-NOMA system, the overall capacity of network shows an upward trend as shown in Fig. 1. This highlights the advantage of SC-NOMA over traditional orthogonal multiple access schemes, where the amount of available orthogonal resources sets the capacity limit.

Recent studies and Research Advances in Bioengineering, Technology, Medical Technology, Nanotechnology and Management and Allied Fields

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Fig 2: Impact of increasing number of user on capacity limitation

SC-NOMA demonstrates the ability to allocate power and utilize superposition coding to serve users with different channel conditions. Users with weaker channels receive more power allocation, leading to higher data rates compared to OMA schemes, which treat all users equally. Overall, the data analysis showcases the advantages of SC-NOMA in terms of spectral efficiency, fairness, overall capacity in multi-user plot.

a. Power = 10 mW

b. Power = 20 mW

c. Power = 30 mW

d. Power = 40 mW

e. Power = 50 mW

f. Power = 60 mW

g. Power = 70 mW

h. Power =80 mW

Fig 3: Capacity vs various power transmitted for 30 users

Table 1: Computed capacity for 30 user with various transmitted power

User Ranking	Transmitted Power (mW)							
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80
	Capacity (bps/Hz) obtained with Various Above Power							
User 1	8.2293	11.4531	14.774	18.3298	21.612	24.8148	28.1503	31.3685
User 2	9.8588	13.3105	16.6154	19.8851	23.1759	26.726	29.8642	33.1455
User 3	10.6947	14.2756	17.5826	21.0669	24.295	27.512	30.7051	34.2478
User 4	10.8681	14.7541	18.1133	21.6126	24.8643	28.1439	31.5896	34.7243
User 5	11.0753	15.1624	18.8465	22.1981	25.3632	28.7674	32.0663	35.3508
User 6	10.4676	15.2221	19.1373	22.4214	25.7226	29.0293	32.2945	35.8199
User 7	9.8435	15.0783	19.2706	22.6921	26.0102	29.3835	32.7623	36.0528
User 8	8.9052	14.6298	19.2326	22.9368	26.2904	29.6367	32.9244	36.2213
User 9	7.886	13.7205	18.952	22.9347	26.5386	29.9197	33.284	36.4943
User 10	7.1518	12.7643	18.6204	22.846	26.5694	30.006	33.3831	36.6985
User 11	6.5836	11.6853	17.5806	22.6812	26.7783	30.2301	33.5241	36.9616
User 12	6.2774	11.0156	16.6744	21.9681	26.5849	30.1701	33.6521	36.996
User 13	6.0451	10.4706	15.6205	21.2385	26.2672	30.3126	33.6653	37.1382
User 14	5.8159	10.097	14.8706	20.2087	25.6145	30.1546	33.7757	37.1738
User 15	5.6335	9.7154	14.3019	19.3563	24.8308	29.7176	33.693	37.2988
User 16	5.5368	9.5058	13.8486	18.5703	23.722	29.0536	33.666	37.3026
User 17	5.4078	9.3567	13.5493	17.9788	22.9168	28.1286	33.1111	37.2386
User 18	5.3478	9.1933	13.2976	17.5838	22.1602	27.2175	32.448	37.0593
User 19	5.3008	9.0688	13.0933	17.2739	21.7651	26.5043	31.597	36.5087
User 20	5.2483	9.0001	12.9749	16.9688	21.2364	25.7926	30.7126	35.8523
User 21	5.1886	8.8964	12.796	16.801	20.9617	25.3108	29.8835	34.9833
User 22	5.1608	8.8238	12.6517	16.5843	20.6651	24.8886	29.355	34.0209
User 23	5.0934	8.7318	12.5563	16.4807	20.4275	24.5901	28.8652	33.398
User 24	5.0545	8.6869	12.4523	16.3334	20.2862	24.3008	28.5252	32.8298
User 25	5.0172	8.6323	12.3893	16.2143	20.1143	24.0763	28.1164	32.3347
User 26	5.0022	8.5917	12.3356	16.1096	19.9738	23.8287	27.8664	31.9481
User 27	4.9421	8.5338	12.2458	16.0026	19.8453	23.7177	27.675	31.6635
User 28	4.9315	8.4755	12.163	15.9409	19.7383	23.5714	27.4397	31.4012
User 29	4.9184	8.4399	12.0978	15.7973	19.612	23.4222	27.2566	31.1925

User 30	4.8856	8.4053	12.0684	15.7558	19.47	23.2704	27.1087	30.9745
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The provided data represents the capacity (in bps/Hz) obtained for individual users in SC-NOMA network with varying levels of transmitted power. As the transmitted power increases from 10 mW to 80 mW, the capacity of all users in the SC-NOMA network also increases shown in Fig. 2. This observation indicates that higher transmitted power leads to higher data rates. Different users in the network achieve different capacity levels even at the same transmitted power. This variation is due to the different channel conditions of users. Users with better channel conditions tend to achieve higher capacity compared to users with weaker channels. Individuals are ordered by network in a decreasing sequence quality (from User 1 to User 30). This ranking influences the power allocation and subsequent capacity. Users with weaker channels may receive higher power allocation to improve their capacity. There is a diminishing return of capacity growth with increasing transmitted power. Initially, the capacity increases rapidly with power, but as the power level becomes sufficiently high, the capacity gains start to level off. Increasing the transmitted power can enhance capacity, but it also requires more resources and may introduce higher levels of interference. Balancing power allocation with system complexity is crucial for optimal performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the simulated data in the SC-NOMA system with increasing transmitted power and the number of multiplexed users provides valuable insights into the performance and limitations of this multi-user communication scheme. In conclusion, the result analysis of the SC-NOMA system with increasing transmitted power and the number of users provides evidence of its efficacy in multi-user communication scenarios. SC-NOMA's ability to allocate power efficiently and leverage superposition coding to help a variety of consumers via different methods as a promising technique for upcoming cordless technologies for communication, offering improved spectral efficiency and fairness compared to traditional OMA schemes.

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July : Theme 2

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